

MOBIDATALAB

Labs for prototyping future mobility data sharing solutions in the cloud

D6.7 Project Cooperation Activities Report #2

**Document of all interactions with other EU/International projects,
initiatives and networks.**

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I Summary sheet

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I Legal Disclaimer

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I Project Partners

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
AKKODIS	France	AKKODIS
POLIS - PROMOTION OF OPERATIONAL LINKS WITH INTEGRATED SERVICES	Belgium	POLIS
F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	Ireland	F6S

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I Executive Summary

This report represents the second iteration of a deliverable documenting engagements with other European Union-funded and international projects, initiatives, and networks as part of the designated task T6.5. Building upon the content of its predecessor, D6.6, this serves as the conclusive report summarising the activities mentioned earlier.

MobiDataLab sought to liaise thematically with other projects and initiatives from Horizon 2020 and beyond, at national, European, and international levels. The identification of other interesting and relevant initiatives was enabled through the project's knowledge-building activities and the recruitment of stakeholders. The format and outcome of this cooperation effort could take several forms (sharing of methodology, research findings, joint presentations, or even joint events). The project was expected to **cooperate with, at least, 3 projects and initiatives per year (a total of 9)**, and all activities are summarised in D6.7 at the end of the project.

- With the submission of this deliverable, the **MobiDataLab partners collaborated with 27 projects or initiatives** for i) the organisation of online events (co-organisation of online events or mutual participation in each-other events), ii) sharing dissemination channels to reach the target audiences and promote projects results (i.e., mutual support in dissemination, website, social networks, etc), and iii) knowledge transfer, such as tips on how to maximise the impact of project activities.
- These collaborations have contributed to the success of MobiDataLab's activities by gathering relevant insights, increasing the visibility of the communication campaigns, and enhancing the impact of project events.
- The present document highlights the projects and initiatives that have actively collaborated with MobiDataLab and outlines the scope of these collaborations and their impact.
- The content is structured into two primary sections. The first section outlines the methodology and plan implemented, while the second section encompasses synergies established during the deliverable timeframe, as well as the whole project. Additionally, it delves into future perspectives and lessons learned, exploring the process of identifying synergies, fostering collaborations, and maximising outcomes from these collaborative efforts.

Related milestone has been achieved in the process, described as follows:

- **Milestone 16 (MS16):** Cooperation with other projects. Mean of verification: cooperation is established by tangible actions such as the exchange of data or joint workshops to share practices around transport data. The milestone was reported within D6.6.

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I Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Overview

There has been an explosion of mobility services and data sharing in recent years. Building on this, the EU-funded MobiDataLab project works to foster the sharing of data amongst transport authorities, operators and other mobility stakeholders in Europe. MobiDataLab develops knowledge as well as a cloud solution aimed at easing the sharing of data. Specifically, the project is based on a continuous co-development of knowledge and technical solutions. It collects and analyses the advice and recommendations of experts and supporting cities, regions, clusters and associations. These actions are assisted by the incremental construction of a cross-thematic knowledge base and a cloud-based service platform, which will improve access and usage of data sharing resources.

1.2. Purpose of the Deliverable

This deliverable aims to document the synergies and exchange of experiences forged with other initiatives over the past 18 months of the MobiDataLab project's implementation (M19–M36). It is crucial to highlight that this is the second of two deliverables serving the same purpose—to report on MobiDataLab's cooperation activities. The first deliverable, D6.6, was submitted at the midpoint of the project (M18).

1.3. Intended Audience

D6.7 'Project cooperation activities report #2' is a public deliverable addressed to the MobiDataLab project partners and to the several actors of the mobility sectors that aim to contribute to an improved data sharing culture and to the digitalisation of the transport sector.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable and Relation with other Work Packages/Deliverable

This document first presents the rationale behind MobiDataLab's cooperation strategy (Section 1, 2 and 3), as included in the Deliverable 6.1 Dissemination Plan (May 2021, M4). Section 4 describes in detail each collaboration activity by MobiDataLab and other European initiatives, between July 2022 (M18) and January 2024 (M36). Finally, Sections 5, 6, and 7 expose the lessons learned from such collaborations for the project so far and outlines the envisaged collaborative activities beyond the project timeframe.

The deliverable takes input from: D6.1 Dissemination plan, D6.2 Reporting on MobiDataLab events #1, D6.3 Reporting on MobiDataLab events #2, and the deliverable provides output to D6.4 Reporting on MobiDataLab events #3, and D6.9 Exploitation Plan - final.

2. Cooperation Methodology

2.1. Rationale as included in the Dissemination Plan

MobiDataLab sought to liaise thematically and establish synergies with other EU projects and initiatives from Horizon 2020 and beyond. This resulted in collaborations such as the co-organisation of events, the involvement of representatives of such initiatives in the MobiDataLab project (and vice versa), sharing of knowledge and best practices, and the cross-promotion of activities and results, in an increased outreach of the project outcomes. The project was expected to **cooperate with, at least, 3 projects and initiatives per year (a total of 9)**.

The monitoring of this activity was done by F6S, with the support of all project partners, and the involvement of further project partners in the cooperation process was done on a case-by-case need, after the joint identification of the collaboration pathways between both parties. Project partners were thus asked to inform F6S, as task leader, and POLIS, as WP leader, of any potential collaboration, and provide the necessary content for scheduling an initial meeting and further developing the collaboration.

A Collaboration Log has been created, for regular monitoring and reporting on the progress of cooperation initiatives. Also, a partnership page on the project's website¹ was made (see Figure 1), to showcase the collaborations established and the work jointly developed.

Figure 1. MobiDataLab Website Partnership Page

¹ <https://mobidatalab.eu/about/cooperations-and-initiatives/>

3. Cooperation Activities Plan

3.1. Establishing Contact with Related Projects

As the overall objective of MobiDataLab is “to propose to the **mobility stakeholders** a methodology and tools that foster the development of a data sharing culture in Europe and beyond,” it is also important to acknowledge **ongoing related projects** and the need to coordinate and collaborate with these to avoid potential duplication and to maximise impact. In line with Task 6.5 “Cooperation with other projects and initiatives”, MobiDataLab successfully:

- Established contact and cooperation with further projects, and programmes, relevant to this project and particularly related initiatives within, Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, and other EC-funded programmes and intra-organisation initiatives.
- Coordinated with other related projects as facilitated by the partners and their wider networks to access members of different organisations with different interests and focus points.
- Tracked the results of cooperation with other projects as an item for discussion on the agenda at each Work Package 6 meeting. F6S maintained oversight of progress on liaising with other projects and will seek to ensure that all opportunities for collaboration are harnessed.

F6S, as leader of Task 6.5 “Cooperation with other projects and initiatives” was required to organise, manage and delegate responsibility for consortium members to contact with related projects. Initially, contact could be made by email with formal correspondence by way of an invitation to cooperate and collaborate.

3.2. Collaboration Types

Collaboration within research-related projects has far-reaching benefits. Collaboration provides a seamless link between universities and research institutions, industry, commerce, government and public services. Collaboration occurs at various levels including individuals, groups, departments, institutions, sectors and countries. Some collaboration is formal, and much more is informal. There are **three possible approaches** to cooperation that were adopted in the MobiDataLab project:

- Corporate Collaboration:
 - Engaging in a comprehensive collaboration with the management team of a relevant project to share resources, expertise, and influence at a project-wide level.
 - Partnering with a consortium from another research initiative to jointly address overarching goals and challenges, enhancing the impact and reach of the MobiDataLab project.
- Team Collaboration:
 - Establishing a task team within MobiDataLab focused on a specific Work Package (WP) and collaborating with contributors from a different project working on a related task.

- Creating a collaborative effort between the MobiDataLab task team and members of another project, specifically addressing shared research problems and pooling resources to achieve common objectives within identified WPs.
- Personal Collaboration:
 - Encouraging partners from MobiDataLab and other projects/initiatives to personally engage with stakeholders, experts, or contributors from external projects to exchange ideas or gain technical expertise.
 - Facilitating one-on-one collaborations between MobiDataLab consortium members and key individuals from other organisations, allowing for a more personalised and direct exchange of insights and knowledge.

3.3. Project Cooperation Aims and Forms

Through inter-project cooperation, the project can benefit in numerous ways. As the project was developing a new methodology and tools, inter-project collaboration was vital for refining what the final MobiDataLab outputs as related to the development of a data-sharing culture would look like. This helped to avoid issues such as duplication or scope slippage, especially concerning the tools of other research projects in the mobility data domain.

MobiDataLab aimed to engage in inter-project collaboration to achieve the following:

- A more integrated or coordinated approach to stakeholder needs, wider geographical reach and access to new stakeholder groups who would not have previously been included in the scope of the project.
- Financial savings in terms of dissemination and integration of existing knowledge and expertise.
- Knowledge, good practice and information sharing, and the capacity to replicate success more vastly and quickly.
- To build a stronger, united voice in the field of mobility data research.
- Better coordination of project activities, competitive advantage, and mutual support between organisations.

Following preparatory work, during the meetings that were held, MobiDataLab presented to the other projects the following **forms to consider regarding collaboration**:

- High-level workshops (e.g., Coordinators' Meetings, Technical Groups' Meetings);
- Joint activities (e.g., common events, webinars, policy sessions, joint newsletters, online editions, publications and press releases, hosting of articles);
- Advisory Services (e.g., Formal advisors to each other);
- Exchange of information on stakeholders' mapping, and
- Projects' social media and communication efforts to be connected and mutually supported.

However, a further set of possibilities has been already processed, and were put into the discussion. Namely, the following organisational and performance management options:

- specify, in writing, a short roadmap and particularly specific goals (“aspirations” of collaboration);
- set smart objectives (most importantly measurable and time-specific objectives);
- specify a wider set of joint activities, and
- define output indicators (numerical values for the outputs of collaboration) and result indicators (tangible/measurable results).

In other words, instead of a “vague” collaboration, this way projects had a specific “framework” of operations and indicators of success.

3.4. Management of Collaboration Activities

The management of the MobiDataLab collaboration activities were mainly carried out under Task 6.5 ‘Cooperation with other projects and initiatives in WP6, which covers communication, dissemination, and exploitation in the MobiDataLab project.

This WP task, and hence the coordination activity, was being led by F6S, with contributions from POLIS, and AKKODIS. To ensure that the MobiDataLab project maintained its strategic direction and to enhance the collaboration with other relevant projects, all partners were invited to participate.

Results and outputs produced from the collaboration between the MobiDataLab consortium and other relevant projects and initiatives on a project, team/task or personal level were tracked and recorded via the Cooperation Log. More monitoring information can be found in Section 0.

For personal and task-level collaborative approaches between MobiDataLab consortium members and other relevant project partners, the MobiDataLab task leader (F6S) was responsible for representing the consortium at collaboration meetings (where practicable) and was tasked with arranging and managing the coordination of the specific meeting.

4. Summary of Synergies and Collaborations

This section summarises the synergies and collaborations that MobiDataLab established with other initiatives and stakeholders, during the whole duration of the project. Nevertheless, emphasis is given to collaborations established between July 2022 (M18) and January 2024 (M36), as collaborations established before that period are reported in D6.6, the first iteration of this deliverable.

Down the line, Table 1 represents the summary of all synergies and collaborations carried out in MobiDataLab.

Table 1. Summary of MobiDataLab Synergies and Collaborations

Initiative Name	Project/Initiative Type	Collaboration Type
4FRONT Cluster	Horizon 2020 projects	• Team Collaboration (More information in 4.1)
5GMETA	Horizon 2020 project	• Team Collaboration (More information in 4.2)
Autonomy Paris	Mobility-related organisation	• Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.3)
DataPorts	Horizon2020 Project	• Team Collaboration (more information in D6.6)
EIT Mobility	Mobility-related organisation	• Corporate Collaboration • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.4)
EMERALDS	Horizon Europe Project	• Corporate Collaboration • Team Collaboration • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.5)
EMTA	Mobility-related organisation	• Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.6)
ENTRANCE Task Group	Horizon2020 Project	• Corporate Collaboration • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.7)
ERTICO	Mobility-related organisation	• Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.17)
ITxPT	Mobility-related organisation	• Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.17)
Le facilitateur de Mobilité	Mobility-related organisation	• Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.17)
MASTER	Horizon2020 Project	• Team Collaboration (more information in D6.6)
moB - Mon Compte Mobilités	Mobility-related organisation	• Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.17)

Mobility Data Association	Mobility-related organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.17)
MobiSpaces	Horizon2020 Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate Collaboration • Team Collaboration • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.8)
Molière	Horizon2020 Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate Collaboration (more information in D6.6)
NAPCORE	Mobility-related organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.17)
NexusForum	Horizon Europe Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate Collaboration (More information in 4.9)
NOUS	Horizon Europe Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team Collaboration • Personal Collaboration (more information in 4.10)
ONCOSCREEN	Horizon Europe Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team Collaboration • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.11)
PrepDspace4Mobility	Horizon2020 Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team Collaboration • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.12)
REACH Incubator	Horizon2020 Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Collaboration (more information in D6.6)
RECIPROCITY	Horizon2020 Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team Collaboration • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.13)
REMOBILISE	Horizon2020 Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Collaboration (See 4.14)
SoBigData++	Horizon2020 Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate Collaboration (more information in D6.6)
SYN+AIR	Horizon2020 Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate Collaboration (more information in D6.6)
UPPER	Horizon2020 Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate Collaboration • Team Collaboration • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.15)
X2.0	Horizon2020 Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team Collaboration • Personal Collaboration (More information in 4.16)

4.1. Collaboration with the 4FRONT Cluster

The **4FRONT Cluster** comprises four Horizon 2020 projects—TANGENT, DIT4TRAM, FRONTIER, and ORCHESTRA—focused on advancing network and traffic management for future mobility. The cluster coordinates activities, such as panel discussions, webinars, and workshops.

The cluster shares common goals:

- Develop tools for dynamic transport demand management and supply optimisation.
- Create innovative architecture and concepts of operations for efficient, resilient, and adaptable multi-modal network and traffic management systems.
- Employ innovative data collection and fusion techniques, leveraging existing standards and methods for data exchange.
- Develop multi-actor organisational and business models with shared responsibilities among various traffic management stakeholders.
- Assess the impact of new technologies, including smart infrastructure and connected and automated vehicles.
- Design and calibrate arbitration models for complex network and traffic management scenarios and multi-actor settings, including disaster management.

TANGENT² is crafting complementary tools for optimising traffic operations in a coordinated, dynamic manner, considering both automated and non-automated vehicles, passengers, and freight transport.

FRONTIER³ aims to shape the network and integrated traffic management strategies of the future, addressing new modes of transport like automated vehicles, with goals to minimise pollution, reduce accidents, and lower mobility costs for users.

ORCHESTRA⁴ aims to equip European policymakers, public authorities, transport providers, and citizens with knowledge and solutions to enhance collaboration and synchronise operations across transport modes, thereby improving safety and reducing emissions.

DIT4TraM⁵ explores intelligent traffic management driven by user-centred mobility services and integrated, intelligent transport networks. It aims to develop and test a holistic approach to decentralisation, distribution, and mechanism design for traffic and mobility management.

² <https://tangent-h2020.eu/>

³ <https://www.frontier-project.eu/>

⁴ <https://orchestra2020.eu/>

⁵ <https://dit4tram.eu/>

Figure 2. 4FRONT Workshop on Data Sharing

MobiDataLab, in collaboration with the 4FRONT Cluster projects, organised an internal online workshop on Data Sharing. Each project presented its specificities, best practices, and challenges, fostering interactive discussions. The workshop report, highlighting insights from the event, will be available in February 2024, coinciding with the RTR Conference.

4.2. Collaboration with the 5GMETA Project

The EU-funded **5GMETA**⁶ project is developing an open platform to leverage car-captured data to stimulate and facilitate innovative products and services. It will empower the automotive ecosystem, from industry players to new entrants such as small and medium-sized enterprises and high-tech start-ups. Granting access to data from relevant geographical regions, the project will create new opportunities and business models from valuable services where data liability and billing will rely on an accountability dashboard of data-flow subscription and volume consumption.

The ITS Congress 2023 in Lisbon served as the backdrop for a collaborative and insightful workshop jointly organised by 5GMETA and MobiDataLab. This workshop, titled "Strategies towards Mobility Data-as-a-Service: Discrepancies and Commonalities," brought together experts, stakeholders, and enthusiasts in the field to explore the evolving landscape of mobility data and foster discussions on shared strategies.

⁶ <https://5gmeta-project.eu/>

Figure 3. 5GMETA and MobiDataLab Workshop at the 2023 ITS Congress

The joint workshop (Figure 3) proved to be a dynamic and collaborative forum. It not only addressed discrepancies and commonalities in strategies towards mobility data-as-a-service but also set the stage for future collaborations and innovations in the realm of connected and automated mobility.

In addition, a joint presentation of the common results and recommendations from MobiDataLab and 5GMETA has been provided during the EARPA FORM Forum in Brussels.

4.3. Collaboration with Autonomy Paris

Autonomy Paris⁷ stands as a community-driven platform, uniting mobility experts, industry leaders, and enthusiasts in a shared commitment to advocate for sustainable, smart, and inclusive mobility solutions. Among its diverse activities, Autonomy orchestrates conferences, hackathons, and other initiatives relevant to MobiDataLab. The collaboration between Autonomy and MobiDataLab proved mutually beneficial, with Autonomy's platform serving as a key channel to promote the MobiDataLab Hackathon and various events.

Notably, representatives of Autonomy actively participated in MobiDataLab Living Labs as a judge, injecting diverse perspectives into the project's endeavours. Their involvement significantly contributed to the successful execution of the MobiDataLab Living Labs. Furthermore, Autonomy has expressed a continued interest in aiding the dissemination of project results, underlining their commitment to supporting and promoting the outcomes of MobiDataLab's initiatives.

⁷ <https://www.autonomy.paris/>

Figure 4. MobiDataLab at the Autonomy Mobility World Online

4.4. Collaboration with EIT Mobility

EIT Mobility⁸ aims to foster collaboration among businesses, education institutions, and research organisations to develop innovative solutions for sustainable, smart, and integrated mobility. The initiative focuses on areas such as urban planning, transportation systems, and technologies that contribute to more efficient and environmentally friendly mobility solutions.

Figure 5. EIT Mobility at the MobiDataLab Codagon

⁸ <https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/>

The representative from EIT Mobility actively participated in the Codagon webinar, contributing insights and expertise to the discussions centred around post-Codagon opportunities and key initiatives supporting urban mobility solutions. Engaging in the panel discussion, the EIT Mobility representative shared valuable perspectives on the array of opportunities awaiting participants after the Codagon event.

During the discussion on post-Codagon opportunities, the representative delved into the potential for growth, development, and implementation of urban mobility solutions. Emphasis was placed on the significance of incubators and accelerators in nurturing and accelerating innovative projects, providing participants with a roadmap for advancing their initiatives.

In the segment highlighting key initiatives supporting urban mobility solutions, the EIT Mobility representative shed light on the role of their organisation and other invited initiatives in facilitating innovation and acceleration. They explored the resources, funding, and collaborative opportunities offered by these initiatives, offering participants valuable insights on leveraging these resources to propel the growth of their solutions. Success stories of innovators thriving in such programmes were shared, providing inspiration and tangible examples of real-world impact in the realm of urban mobility.

4.5. Collaboration with the EMERALDS Project

The EU-funded **EMERALDS**⁹ project will develop a toolset for mobility data. Its aim is to facilitate the processing and analysing the large data streams. The toolset will enable the stakeholders of the urban mobility ecosystem to collect and manage ubiquitous spatio-temporal data of high-volume, high-velocity and of high-variety, analyse them both in online and offline settings. It will be tested in the pilot cities of Utrecht and The Hague. Specifically, the toolset will make it possible to import data to real-time responsive algorithms and visualise results in interactive dashboards. Moreover, both projects have agreed on mutual communication and dissemination support, which is being carried out successfully.

The collaborative meeting between EMERALDS and MobiDataLab revealed synergies and opportunities for aligning challenges and use cases in the fields of urban and transport planning, as well as operational traffic engineering. While MobiDataLab's challenges were more technically focused, involving semantic enrichment and Linked Open Data, EMERALDS presented challenges related to Low Emission Zones and large events. The meeting identified potential linkages between use cases through intermediary partners, private data providers, and researchers, setting the stage for collaborative exchanges.

Notably, the projects recognised the value of sharing information on real-time public transport vehicle datasets and exploring data sources provided by municipalities to enhance their collective impact on urban mobility solutions.

⁹ <https://emeralds-horizon.eu/>

Besides general communication support, the EMERALDS project members and MobiSpaces project members teamed up and actively engaged in the MobiDataLab Datathon, contributing their expertise and insights to the dynamic event. Through their participation, the EMERALDS team brought valuable perspectives from their experiences in addressing challenges related to urban mobility and traffic engineering.

4.6. Collaboration with EMTA

EMTA, **European Metropolitan Transport Authorities**¹⁰, is the network of public transport authorities that organise mobility services in metropolitan areas in Europe. Since 1998, EMTA is a forum to exchange experience and best practices in the field of planning, integrating and funding public transport services at the metropolitan level. It follows a programme of work elaborated by its members. EMTA brings together 34 authorities from 21 European countries. Together, EMTA members work to improve the daily mobility solutions offered to more than 100 million Europeans. They are responsible for organising safe, smart, sustainable and healthy mobility options in areas stretching well beyond the borders of the core municipality.

EMTA played a pivotal role in the review committee for MobiDataLab Innovation Events, namely Datathon, Hackathon, and Codagon, under the guidance of Thomas Geier.

4.7. Collaboration with the ENTRANCE Task Force

EU-funded **ENTRANCE**¹¹ provides a European matchmaking platform and complementary off-line services, designed to mobilise financial resources to accelerate the market access and scale-up of pioneering sustainable transport solutions. The project will identify innovative zero-emission transport solutions and promote their registration on the ENTRANCE platform where they can be matched with potential buyers and financing opportunities. Knowledge on good practices on the deployment of innovative solutions, European and national tenders and legislation, will be exchanged through the online platform. Training and brokerage activities will take place and ENTRANCE will facilitate purchase aggregation by setting up a neutral trustee for the orchestration of collaborations. Access to finance will be supported through individual and personalised innovation finance advice and support.

MobiDataLab has enthusiastically joined the **ENTRANCE Task Force**¹², aligning with its commitment to fostering communication, dissemination, and exploitation support for sustainable transport solutions. ENTRANCE, with its mission to promote widespread understanding and adoption of sustainable transport solutions across Europe, has forged collaborations with various projects in the sector. Recognising the common goals of reducing CO₂ emissions and advancing sustainable mobility, MobiDataLab's participation in the dedicated Task Force, underscores its dedication to accelerating the market uptake of innovative transport solutions.

¹⁰ <https://www.emta.com/>

¹¹ <https://www.entrance-platform.eu/>

¹² <https://www.entrance-platform.eu/the-project/what/liaison-projects/>

Current members of the Task Force represent organisations from several H2020 projects, including ASSURED-UAM, BOOSTLOG, FastTrack, FUTURE-HORIZON, PLATINA3, RECIPROCITY, LASTING, REMOBILISE, and ASSURED.

Within the Task Force, MobiDataLab aims to contribute by enhancing awareness, mobilising resources, and fostering cross-project and cross-sectoral cooperation. This collaborative effort seeks to amplify the impact of project activities across diverse stakeholders, ranging from high-level policymakers to end users.

4.8. Collaboration with the MobiSpaces Project

The EU-funded **MobiSpaces**¹³ project develops an end-to-end mobility-aware and mobility-optimised data governance platform with key differentiating factors. Specifically, it will design the extraction of actionable insights from ubiquitous mobile sensor data and IoT devices in a decentralised way. Five mobility use cases – from smart public transport services in cities to vessel tracking – will demonstrate the impact of the project's platform in real-life scenarios.

Besides general communication and dissemination support, the MobiSpaces project members teamed up and actively engaged in the MobiDataLab Datathon, contributing their expertise and insights to the dynamic event.

Furthermore, MobiDataLab and MobiSpaces, alongside several other projects – MASTER, SoBigData++, VesselAI, EMERALDS, and Green.Dat.AI – supported the organisation of the **6th BMDA workshop**.¹⁴ The workshop will be organised in March 2024 and foster the exchange of new ideas on multidisciplinary real-world problems, discuss proposals about innovative solutions, and identify emerging opportunities for further research in the area of big mobility data analytics, such as deep learning on mobility data, edge computing, visual analytics. The workshop intends to bridge the gap between researchers and big mobility data stakeholders, including experts from critical domains, such as urban / maritime / aviation transportation, human complex networks.

4.9. Collaboration with the NexusForum.EU Project

The transition and the move of the whole community of EC-funded projects and related initiatives towards a closer cooperation with industry is what the **NexusForum.EU**¹⁵ project aims to support and facilitate by focusing on consolidating research and policy along the Cognitive Computing Continuum.

MobiDataLab participated at the NexusForum2023, a unique physical event aimed at exploring technological synergies between the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud, the EU companies and Members States involved in the IPCEI on Cloud Infrastructure & Services, and the community of research and innovation projects developed under the Horizon Europe programme.

¹³ <https://mobispaces.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://www.datastories.org/bmda24/>

¹⁵ <https://nexusforum.eu/>

Building on its experience gained through active participation in MobiDataLab, F6S is poised to leverage its insights and expertise within the NexusForum project. Particularly, F6S will channel the knowledge acquired from MobiDataLab into NexusForum, emphasising the collaboration and community aspects.

4.10. Collaboration with the NOUS Project

The **NOUS** project endeavours to pioneer the development of a robust European Cloud Service architecture that seamlessly integrates computational and data storage resources across a spectrum of devices.

From edge devices and supercomputers to the HPC network and Quantum Computers, NOUS envisions a holistic Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS)/Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) cloud provider. Leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as edge computing and decentralisation paradigms, NOUS aims to orchestrate a diverse array of devices and machines, elevating Europe's capacity for processing vast data volumes.

AETHON leads the cooperation, with active involvement from other project partners including KUL, F6S, and ICOOR. The NOUS project aims to extend the functionalities of the MobiDataLab's Virtual Labs platform to align with its overarching goals.

4.11. Collaboration with the ONCOSCREEN Project

The EU-funded **ONCOSCREEN**¹⁶ project aims to promote accurate, non-invasive, cost-effective screening tests based on new technologies and an increased awareness of colorectal cancer. Personalised approaches for screening are needed to consider genetic and other socioeconomic variables and environmental stressors. With this in mind, the project will develop a risk-based, population-level stratification methodology for CRC to account for genetic prevalence, socioeconomic status and other factors.

Recognising the versatile functionalities of the Virtual Lab platform developed by MobiDataLab, ONCOSCREEN has initiated collaboration via AETHON to leverage this platform for the execution of its four Living Labs in the health domain.

Although the Living Labs primarily focus on health-related challenges, the adaptability of the Virtual Lab platform, designed to be domain-agnostic, allows for seamless deployment and testing.

Beyond the ONCOSCREEN project, this platform stands ready to contribute to and facilitate other Living Labs, showcasing its potential impact in diverse domains even after the conclusion of the MobiDataLab project.

¹⁶ <https://oncoscreen.health/>

4.12. Collaboration with the PrepDspace4Mobility Project

The European Mobility Data Space (EMDS) CSA, known as **PrepDspace4Mobility**¹⁷, while progressing towards its finalisation stage, focusing on reporting, defining recommendations, and establishing crucial building blocks, sought to actively engage with key stakeholders, including MobiDataLab, to share, reflect upon, and align its findings.

The team at PrepDspace4Mobility has extended an invitation to MobiDataLab, to present the initial findings of their work and engage in discussions on how these findings harmonise with the concepts embraced by MobiDataLab.

Notably, the coordinator of PrepDspace4Mobility, played a pivotal role in the review committee of the Innovation Events, further emphasising the collaborative relationship. Additionally, AKKODIS, representing MobiDataLab, actively participated in a PrepDspace4Mobility workshop focused on mobility data sharing. This exchange of insights and collaborative efforts underscore the synergies between PrepDspace4Mobility and MobiDataLab in shaping the future landscape of mobility data initiatives.

4.13. Collaboration with the RECIPROCITY Project

The EU-funded **RECIPROCITY**¹⁸ project initiated innovative mobility solutions in at least 20 European cities and municipalities to address the challenges posed by urbanisation, climate change, and digitalization. These were considered as megatrends necessitating a re-evaluation of mobility. Various areas, differing in size, location, degree of urbanisation, and mobility needs, were provided with tools, knowledge, and contacts to expedite the development process of innovative mobility solutions.

MobiDataLab organised a webinar¹⁹ that aimed to bring together mobility stakeholders (transport authorities, mobility-oriented networks, and both data providers and data consumers) to get familiar with innovative solutions to concrete problems using open data as a tool, as well as to accelerate the replication of existing innovative mobility solutions.

RECIPROCITY was one of the four innovative projects presented methodologies and tools that tackle those barriers, foster the development of a data-sharing culture in Europe, and effective ways to implement their respective smart city strategies and community initiatives.

MobiDataLab also joined the RECIPROCITY Mobility Assembly that included different activities such as presentations of actors, initiatives and projects, one-to-one meetings, and working group meetings.

¹⁷ <https://mobilitydataspace-csa.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://reciprocity-project.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://mobidatalab.eu/mobidatalab-webinar-insights-fostering-a-data-sharing-culture-for-better-mobility-in-europe-2/>

Figure 6. RECIPROCITY and MobiDataLab Joint Webinar

The aim was to bring together different actors to foster potential cooperation in different areas related to sustainable urban mobility. POLIS participated at the event on behalf of MobiDataLab and delivered a presentation about the project and its initial findings, as well as future activities related to Living Labs.

Figure 7. MobiDataLab at the RECIPROCITY Mobility Assembly

Moreover, POLIS joined a workshop where the aim is to explore and understand the financial needs and obstacles of innovative projects in the field of mobility based on the experiences of the participants. MobiDataLab and its Transport Cloud was presented within the “Use of Data for Urban Transport Management” segment.

4.14. Collaboration with the REMOBILISE Project

REMOBILISE²⁰ is a project pursuing the overall objectives of strengthening cluster management excellence while facilitating strategic connections between our clusters and our specialised ecosystems and cities across Europe, in the sector of mobility.

REMOBILISE and MobiDataLab have embarked on shared communication initiatives. This collaborative approach sought to optimise the impact of both projects by leveraging each other's networks, expertise, and outreach capabilities. By aligning communication efforts, REMOBILISE and MobiDataLab aimed to amplify their collective influence in the mobility sector, promoting a cohesive narrative and ensuring a more comprehensive dissemination of their respective contributions.

4.15. Collaboration with the UPPER Project

The Horizon Europe **UPPER**²¹ project is dedicated to fortifying the position of public transport as a pioneering force for sustainability and innovation in urban mobility during the transition towards zero emissions. A pivotal component of the UPPER project is the development of the UPPER Toolkit, an advanced digital environment designed to assess the impacts of implemented public transport measures. This assessment involves the definition and calculation of Urban Mobility Indicators before, during, and after the implementation of these measures.

Figure 8. MobiDataLab Codagon: UPPER Challenge Banner

In collaboration with UPPER, MobiDataLab orchestrated a Codagon event, incorporating a dedicated segment focused on a challenge presented by the UPPER project (more information in D5.8). The overarching objective of Codagon was to drive improvements in urban mobility through the collaborative sharing of data.

²⁰ <https://remobilise.eu/>

²¹ <https://www.upperprojecteu.eu/>

Participants were afforded the opportunity to choose from various challenges pertaining to urban mobility data, aligning with the shared goal of enhancing urban mobility through innovative data-driven solutions. This strategic partnership between MobiDataLab and UPPER underscores their commitment to advancing sustainable and innovative urban mobility practices.

4.16. Collaboration with the X2.0 Project

X2.0²² is a deep-tech growth programme lead by F6S that seeks to ensure the scaling up of EU deep-tech start-ups by providing custom, industry-focused, growth programme that will act as a catalyst in delivering market-ready applications and technology solutions in 5 key impact areas: Manufacturing & Circular Economy, AgriTech, HealthTech & BioTech, Smart Cities and Sustainability, and Data & A.I.

X2.0 and MobiDataLab collaborated during the Codagon event, with the discussions centred around post-Codagon opportunities and key initiatives supporting urban mobility solutions. X2.0 presented their 5-month deep-tech programme, which focus encompassed a wide range of sub-topics and areas of focus which can be seen to overlap and interconnect with MobiDataLab, such as urban mobility & clean transportation, and urban planning and development.

4.17. Collaboration with relevant Mobility-related organisations

MobiDataLab has strategically cultivated relationships with numerous mobility-related organisations, a significant portion of which has been formalised through their inclusion in the **project's advisory board**.

Recognising the invaluable insights and expertise these organisations bring to the realm of mobility, MobiDataLab has actively sought their guidance to enrich project initiatives. The establishment of these connections underscores MobiDataLab's commitment to fostering a collaborative and inclusive approach in addressing challenges within the mobility sector. Relevant organisations include:

- **moB - Mon Compte Mobilités**²³ serves as a foundational infrastructure addressing a critical aspect in digital mobility—identity. Functioning as a comprehensive catalogue of aid, moB is a versatile tool empowering communities and users to manage incentives and aid for mobility within their territories. The association provided Advisory Services to MobiDataLab.
- The **Mobility Data Association**²⁴ plays a pivotal role in expediting the advancement and adoption of mobility specifications, including GTFS (General Transit Feed Specification) and GBFS (General Bikeshare Feed Specification). Through the provision of technical expertise and tools, the association actively contributes to the development of new specifications, hosts training sessions, and establishes working groups to meet the evolving needs of the mobility industry. The association provided Advisory Services to MobiDataLab.

²² <https://x2-0.eu/>

²³ <https://moncomptemobilite.fr/>

²⁴ <https://mobilitydata.org/>

- **ERTICO – ITS Europe**²⁵ stands as a dynamic public-private partnership organisation, boasting a vast network of over 120 members spanning eight different sectors within the ITS and Smart Mobility community. Bridging service providers, suppliers, research institutions, public authorities, and more, ERTICO fosters connectivity and collaboration among diverse stakeholders. The association provided Advisory Services to MobiDataLab.
- The non-profit association **ITxPT**²⁶ actively promotes an open architecture, data accessibility, and interoperability between IT systems, particularly in public transport and other mobility services. Committed to developing IT architecture based on standards and best practices, ITxPT engages its members in collaborative efforts to advance interoperability. The association provided Advisory Services to MobiDataLab, within their mission to enhance the accessibility and integration of IT systems within the mobility sector. Moreover, ITxPT played a pivotal role in the review committee for MobiDataLab Innovation Events, namely Datathon, Hackathon, and Codagon.
- **Le facilitateur de Mobilité**²⁷, in its role as a decoding force in new mobilities, conducts field tests and collaborates with local experts through extensive explorations each year. The association provided Advisory Services to MobiDataLab.
- **NAPCORE**²⁸ (National Access Point Coordination Organisation for Europe) takes on the vital role of coordinating and harmonizing over 30 mobility data platforms across Europe. As the world's largest cooperation of mobility data platforms, NAPCORE presented the National Access Points to participants in the Datathon, showcasing its efforts in unifying and streamlining mobility data accessibility on a continental scale.

MobiDataLab joined the NAPCORE Mobility Data Days, an event that includes presentations from industry leaders and case studies of successful mobility data projects. The goal of NAPCORE Mobility Data Days is to explore the potential of mobility data to improve urban transportation systems and enhance the mobility experience for users.

POLIS and AKKODIS joined the event to network with National Access Point and research delegates, while Suzanne Hoadley of POLIS participated in the opening panel discussion.

²⁵ <https://ertico.com/>

²⁶ <https://itxpt.org/>

²⁷ <https://www.julienelabaca.com/>

²⁸ <https://napcore.eu/>

Figure 9. NAPCORE Mobility Data Days Opening Panel Session

5. Future Collaboration Perspectives

As the conclusion of MobiDataLab approaches in January 2024, it leaves behind a legacy of invaluable results that transcend its formal endpoint, offering a wealth of resources for the **benefit of both existing and future projects and initiatives**. The intricate pathways for the exploitation of these outcomes are outlined in D6.9.

Notably, MobiDataLab's wealth of experience, well-established methodologies, and concrete results are set to play an important role in shaping the trajectory of upcoming initiatives. Specifically, its relevance extends to projects funded under noteworthy calls, exemplified by

- Topic HORIZON-CL5-2024-D6-01-03, addressing the orchestration of heterogeneous actors in mixed traffic within the CCAM ecosystem (CCAM Partnership), and
- Topic HORIZON-CL5-2024-D6-01-06, focusing on the optimization of multimodal network and traffic management, leveraging data from infrastructures and encompassing the mobility of passengers and freight transport.

MobiDataLab partners will serve as reference point for projects and initiatives interested in the utilising project's results. Consortium Members will remain open for collaboration, promoting the sharing of scientific expertise, broadening outreach, and fostering inclusiveness and stakeholder participation.

Whether or not MobiDataLab consortium members actively participate in these endeavours, the overarching aim is to encourage the convergence of scientific efforts and facilitate a collaborative environment that transcends the project's formal conclusion.

6. Monitoring and Lessons Learned

The monitoring of this activity was done by F6S, and partners are asked to inform F6S, as task leader, and POLIS, as WP leader, of any potential collaboration, and provide the necessary content for scheduling an initial meeting and further developing the collaboration.

In addition, the **Collaboration Log** (Figure 10) has been created, for regular monitor and reporting on the progress of cooperation initiatives. All intended collaboration meetings should be reported to F6S so that they can be well documented.

Project/initiative	Funding body	End Date	Project/initiative description	Potential interest for MobiDataLab	Activity status (select from options)	Lead partner	Status
Fenix Network	Connecting Europe Facility		Fenix will develop the European federated architecture for data sharing serving the European logistics community in order to offer interoperability between any individual existing and future platforms	Learn from the experience of Fenix in terms of the business stakeholders' collaborative framework created and in terms of system architecture	Identified (tbc)	ICODR (through 3rd party UNIMORE)	
Master - Multiple Aspect Trajectory Management and Analysis	H2020	dec-23	The research objective of MASTER is to investigate methods for building and analysing semantically rich mobility data	Build on the research results regarding the semantic enrichment activities. Specifically, on the new concept of multiple aspects trajectories methods, methods to manage these kinds of mobility data and	Completed	CNR is one of the consortium partners	https://www.digstuhl.de/en/program/calendar/semhp/semhp-2022 - Article on MobiDataLab and cooperation with MASTER in the 6th MASTER newsletter March-April 2022 (author, Thierry Chevallier)
SoBigData++ - European Integrated Infrastructure for Social Mining and Big Data Analytics	H2020	December 2024	Deliver a distributed, Pan-European, multi-disciplinary research infrastructure for big social data to understand the complexity of our society	Exploit the results in terms of: know how on a platform for sharing datasets and analysis methods. This can be exploited in the Transport Cloud and Use Cases	Completed	CNR is one of the consortium partners	Meeting on 9 November, between 3pm and 4pm CET/Brussels Time. These are the contacts for H2020 SoBigData++: josep.domingo@urv.cat (myself, Josep Domingo-Ferrer, URV), chiara.renno@isti.cnr.it (Chiara Renno, CNR), valerio.grossi@isti.cnr.it (Valerio Grossi, CNR), for
UNALAB - Urban Nature Labs	H2020	November 2022	Foster urban innovation ecosystems, wherein stakeholders co-create and optimise nature-based solutions for improved climate and water resilience. Develop and demonstrate the	Key components and associated methodology for their definition in D2.1 will be exploited along with a collection of the various definitions for Living Labs.	Identified (tbc)		
REACH - EurloopAn Incubator for trusted and secure data value Chains	H2020	February 2024	The EU-funded REACH project will launch a sustainable European second-generation incubator for data-fuelled start-ups and SMEs with the aim of developing innovative experiments within data value	Have access to a pool of data-driven startups and SMEs to engage with in the scope of the Living Labs and other activities of the project that involve close contact with innovators and entrepreneurs	Completed	F6S is one of the consortium partners	
DMS Accelerator	H2020	December 2021	Supporting the European data market providing free support services to data-centric SMEs and start-ups	Have access to a pool of data-driven startups and SMEs to engage with in the scope of the Living Labs and other activities of the project that involve close contact with innovators and entrepreneurs	Identified (tbc)	F6S knows one of the consortium partners, Bright Pael	
Policy Cloud - Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management	H2020	December 2022	The EU-funded PolicyCLOUD project will deliver an integrated cloud-based environment for data-driven decision support to public authorities for policy	In recent years, the data market has been flourishing. A sharp downfall in trust towards platforms considered secure and privacy-aware, however, has hampered the market. This lack of trust has hit the	Identified (tbc)	F6S knows one of the partners, ICCS	
TRUSTS - Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space	H2020	December 2022	In recent years, the data market has been flourishing. A sharp downfall in trust towards platforms considered secure and privacy-aware, however, has hampered the market. This lack of trust has hit the		Identified (tbc)	F6S knows one of the partners, Leibniz University	
SYN+AIR - Synergies between transport modes and Air transportation	H2020	December 2022	SYN+AIR aims to develop common sets for data sharing between transport service providers (TSP), enabling passengers to enjoy a seamless door-to-door		Completed	AETHON is one of the consortium partners	

Figure 10. MobiDataLab Cooperation Log

Any collaborative publication or outcomes resulting from such collaboration approaches should be also saved accordingly in the file management system in the folder "T6.5 - Cooperation with other projects and initiatives" within the main folder Work Package 6.

Other discussion points or concept contributions which can potentially contribute to the MobiDataLab outputs were also be documented in a word document report and saved in the file management system. Where collaboration with other projects has informed or contributed to the successful execution of a task this should be documented in the associated deliverable under a section entitled 'Summary of Synergies and Collaborations'.

Drawing from the contents of the task folder within the project repository, the outcomes of the collaboration approaches will be outlined in a section in the MobiDataLab mid-term and final reports.

6.1. Lessons Learned and Possible Barriers to Collaboration

The following are the **lessons learned** in terms of how to identify synergies and create collaborations, and how to get maximum outcome from the collaborations.

How to **identify synergies** and create collaborations:

- Early identification of relevant initiatives that could potentially have synergies with the project.
- Identify areas or objectives of collaboration (i.e., similar scope and activities, similar research objectives, similar target audiences, similar communication channels used, etc.).
- Early engagement with potential initiatives/stakeholders (i.e., sending a brief presentation email introducing the project, organised an awareness event early in the project).
- Take advantage of the activities conducted in the project for networking and relationship building (i.e., if the project foresees interviews for research purposes use that opportunity to negotiate mutual communication support; in events carefully track the contacts made and potential areas of future collaboration).

How to get **maximum outcome** from the collaborations:

- Organise joint events (both online and offline), collaborating in the identification and invitation of relevant speakers and panellist and getting the maximum visibility through joint dissemination.
- Write joint conclusions and articles and support the dissemination to reach the wider audience.
- The collaboration online through the social networks can exponentially contribute to increase the visibility and outreach of research results. Find and follow other projects and initiatives collaborating with the project, share their information, send direct messages when you want to announce specific information.

It is important for entities to be aware of **potential barriers** to inter-project collaboration, such as:

- Individual personalities and competition between partners from the related EU projects. Naturally, this could be a barrier as some of the identified EU projects which will be involved in the collaboration efforts will have similar goals and objectives similar to those pursued by MobiDataLab, and might also have to compete geographical, financial and stakeholder interests which must be considered by the MobiDataLab consortium.
- Lack of information and experience can be a potential barrier as sometimes other projects may be working to a different scope or mandate.
- As inter-project collaboration is a joint venture aimed at exploring how to refine or develop project outcomes, there should be expected that there can also be resistance to change.

As a result, there are various **risks** associated with inter-project collaboration including i) lack of consistency and clarity on roles and responsibilities; ii) outcomes do not justify the time and resources invested; iii) loss of flexibility in working practices, and complexity in decision-making; iv) energy and resources away from core aims, i.e., mission drift; and v) damage to organisation and waste of resources if collaboration is unsuccessful.

The possible barriers and risks identified above which can potentially limit the effectiveness of inter-project collaboration can be **mitigated** by developing the following: i) good personal relationships; ii) written agreements (e.g., Memorandum of Understanding); iii) clear and agreed mutual benefits and collaborative advantage; iv) focus on the big picture, and v) careful planning.

7. Conclusion

The objectives of Task 6.5 'Cooperation with other projects and initiatives' were being carried out according to project's needs, and **continuous synergies** with other projects, initiatives and networks were implemented.

Creating synergies was an important task that was in continuous implementation throughout the duration of the project, and it is mostly sustained by the key involvement of project partners in other relevant initiatives and projects. Being transparent about the activities of the project opened several collaboration opportunities with other projects and increased the quality of the processes and results of MobiDataLab.

As part of MobiDataLab project activities, project partners have undertaken several actions in order to further develop the project, create synergies, disseminate the results achieved and find link with other initiatives funded by the European Commission. As presented within the previous chapters, all project partners have used their contacts and links to other projects and further deepened the knowledges in terms of future Mobility Data sharing cloud solutions.

The MobiDataLab project, originally slated to engage with a minimum of 3 projects or initiatives annually (**totalling 9 collaborations**), **significantly surpassed expectations**. As evidenced by the comprehensive summary provided in this Deliverable at the project's conclusion, **MobiDataLab partners successfully collaborated with more than 27 projects or initiatives**. This substantial outreach underscores the project's proactive and impactful engagement within the broader research and innovation landscape, exceeding its initial cooperative targets.

MobiDataLab Consortium

The consortium of MobiDataLab consists of 10 partners with multidisciplinary and complementary competencies. This includes leading universities, networks and industry sector specialists.

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<https://www.linkedin.com/company/mobidatalab>

For further information please visit www.mobidatalab.eu

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